
44. The Hubble constant from Cepheids

THE DISCOVERY, by Edwin Hubble almost a century ago, that distant galaxies are moving away from us at speeds proportional to their distance, was the first observational evidence for the expansion of the Universe. Today, Hubble's 'law' still serves as one of the key pieces of evidence supporting its 'Big Bang' origins.

Hubble's estimates of the distances to spiral galaxies (then known as spiral nebulae) were based on luminous variable Cepheid stars within them. His observations actually followed theoretical work over the preceding decade, independently by Russian physicist Alexander Friedmann and Belgian astronomer Georges Lemaître, based on the equations of general relativity, and suggesting that the Universe could be expanding.

At the time of the discovery and later development of Hubble's law, galaxy redshifts were interpreted as Doppler velocity shifts in the context of special relativity. The 'Hubble constant', H_0 , was similarly formulated as the constant of proportionality relating the galaxy's distance, D , with its recession speed, v , i.e. $v = H_0 D$.

The Hubble constant is most frequently quoted in km/s per Mpc ($\text{km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$), i.e. giving the speed in km/s of a galaxy at a distance of 1 Mpc (although we may note that this is simply equivalent to s^{-1} in SI units). Its value is about $70 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$.

THINGS HAVE certainly become much more complicated since the time of Hubble.

We now know, for example, that the Hubble 'constant' actually varies with time in standard cosmological models. And all observations of extremely distant objects are actually observations relating to the distant past, when the 'constant' had a different value. H_0 is, rather, the present-day value of the 'Hubble parameter' describing the expansion of the Universe with time.

Again, more generally, the Hubble parameter may be increasing or decreasing with time depending on the actual value of the deceleration parameter, q , being a dimensionless measure of the cosmic acceleration of the expansion of space. If $q = 0$, then $H = 1/t$, where t is the time since the Big Bang, i.e. the age of the Universe.

It was long thought that q was positive, indicating that the expansion is slowing down due to gravitational attraction. This would imply an age of the Universe less than $1/H$ (which is about 14 billion years). For example, a value for $q = 0.5$ (once favoured by most theorists) would give the age of the Universe as $\frac{2}{3}(\frac{1}{H})$.

A major development occurred in the 1990s, with the discovery that distant supernovae were dimmer, and therefore farther away, than previously suspected. This unexpected finding indicated that the Universe was not only expanding, but also accelerating in its expansion.

The result implied the existence of dark energy as an inevitable consequence of cosmological models, i.e. a new force pushing everything in the cosmos apart. The discovery that q is apparently negative means that the Universe could be older than $1/H$, although estimates of its age still put it very close to $1/H$.

Another complication in interpreting the Hubble law is that gravitationally interacting galaxies move relative to each other independently of the expansion of the Universe. These 'peculiar velocities' also need to be correctly accounted for in any related studies.

VARIOUS METHODS have been used to determine the Hubble constant. The story is long and involved, and things have come a long way since Edwin Hubble's own over-estimate, of about $500 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$.

What have become known as 'late Universe' methods rely on calibrated distance ladder techniques: measuring the redshifts of distant galaxies, and then determining the distances to them by some other method.

Over the past half century, many hundreds of research papers have targeted the refinement of H_0 . But uncertainties in the physical assumptions used to determine these distances have resulted in varying and discordant estimates of its precise numerical value.

For most of the second half of the 20th century, H_0 was estimated to lie in the range $50\text{--}90 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$. Over the past decade or so, data from Cepheid variables and other astrophysical 'standards' have converged on a 'late Universe' value of around $70 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$.

Meanwhile, since about 2000, ‘early Universe’ techniques have become available. These values are based on measurements of the cosmic microwave background, viz. the ‘echo’ from the Big Bang that contains imprints of the Universe’s fundamental properties. Initially from NASA’s WMAP, and more recently from ESA’s Planck mission, the most recent Planck estimates yield $H_0 = 67.66 \pm 0.42 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ (Aghanim et al., 2020).

OF THE LATE UNIVERSE measurements being pursued most actively today, two are particularly powerful, and both have been advanced by Gaia.

One makes use of earlier work on red giant stars, and uses the tip of the red-giant branch as a primary distance indicator. It is based on the fact that all red giants reach the same peak brightness at the end of their lives. The latest estimates from the Hubble Space Telescope give a value of $69.8 \pm 1.9 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ (Freedman et al., 2019). Combining this with recent parallax measures of the distance to the globular cluster Omega Centauri from Gaia EDR3 (discussed separately here) gives a value of $72.1 \pm 2.0 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ (Soltis et al., 2021).

BUT LET US RETURN to the method based on Cepheid variables, used by Hubble a century ago, and still pertinent today given the Gaia parallax measurements.

The relation between Cepheid luminosities and pulsation periods was discovered by Henrietta Leavitt in 1908, based on variable stars in the Magellanic Clouds. Inferring the true luminosity of a Cepheid by observing its pulsation period in turn allows the distance to the star to be determined.

One example of the new distances from Gaia is for the long-period Cepheid RS Pup, shown here, where DR2 lists a geometric parallax of $0.5844 \pm 0.0260 \text{ mas}$, corresponding to a distance of $1710 \pm 80 \text{ pc}$. Gaia DR2 actually includes 9575 stars classified as Cepheids (Clementini et al., 2019).

FOR SOME YEARS, the strongest evidence for a high value of H_0 , of around $70 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$, has rested on an empirical Cepheid-based calibration of the distances to galaxies hosting Type Ia supernovae.

Riess et al. (2016) based their value of 73.24 ± 1.74 on 19 such Cepheids observed with HST–WFC3, along with a more robust distance to the Large Magellanic Cloud based on late-type detached eclipsing binaries, HST observations of Cepheids in M31, and new HST-based trigonometric parallaxes for Milky Way Cepheids.

Riess et al. (2018a) added new HST-based parallaxes of a further seven long-period Milky Way Cepheids to yield a value of $73.48 \pm 1.66 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$.

Riess et al. (2018b) used HST photometry of 50 long-period, low-extinction Milky Way Cepheids observed in the same photometric system as extragalactic Cepheids in Type Ia supernova host galaxies. For the first time, Gaia parallaxes (from DR2) were included to constrain the distance scale, while simultaneously estimating the global DR2 parallax zero-point offset. Their resulting value was a rather similar $73.52 \pm 1.62 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$.

Riess et al. (2021) used 75 Milky Way Cepheids with Hubble Space Telescope photometry, now using the greatly improved Gaia EDR3 parallaxes. Applied to the calibration of Type Ia supernovae, it gave $H_0 = 73.0 \pm 1.4 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$. Combined with the best complementary sources of Cepheid calibration, they found $H_0 = 73.2 \pm 1.3 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$, reaching 1.8% precision, but a 4.2σ difference with the estimate from the latest Planck microwave background observations.

The inclusion of future Gaia parallaxes is expected to lead to a total uncertainty on H_0 of as little as 1.0–1.3%. As stressed by Riess et al., neither HST nor Gaia can expect to reach this goal alone: rather, this milestone will require simultaneously measuring Cepheid parallaxes to around $5 \mu\text{as}$ precision from Gaia, and measuring the brightnesses of the same objects to about 0.01 mag precision with HST within the *same* photometric systems used to measure their extragalactic counterparts.

The important point is that such differential flux measurements essentially circumvent systematic uncertainties related to instrumental zero-points and transmission functions, which otherwise impose a systematic uncertainty of 2–3% in the determination of H_0 .

THE TWO VALUES presently considered to be the most reliable – the ‘early Universe’ estimate of $H_0 = 67.66 \pm 0.42 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ from the Planck mission, and the ‘late Universe’ value of $H_0 = 73.2 \pm 1.3$ from the combined HST and Gaia measurements of Cepheids – might not seem very different. But each is very precise, and the disagreement, although small, is statistically significant.

Meanwhile, various other promising methods of addressing this so-called ‘Hubble tension’ are also being developed, including the use of gravitational lensing, and the properties of gravitational waves.

AT STAKE is not so much the precise value of H_0 *per se*, but whether the different estimates hide some new and exotic physics, either in the understanding of stellar evolution, or in the physics of the early Universe.

Prospects for a resolution include whether we live in a local ‘bubble’ (e.g. Shanks et al. 2019), or whether weak gravitational lensing is affecting the measurements of Type Ia supernovae.

Hubble Space Telescope (NASA/ESA)